

An Investigation Into the Effectiveness
of Contemporary Legislation and Anti-
spiking Practices in Protecting Women
and Girls in England and Wales.

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Abstract

This research study is concerned with spiking, specifically focusing on female victimisation. The objective of the research is to investigate the effectiveness of contemporary legislation and anti-spiking practices in protecting women and girls from spiking in England and Wales. This research addresses the limited existing literature on spiking's impacts on women. This is despite data published showing the repeated trend in female victimisation and increases in its occurrence. The aim of this research is to gather public perceptions of the gaps in legislation and measures to reduce spiking, and to obtain recommendations for increasing protection of women from spiking, whilst simultaneously reviewing the limited existing data on anti-spiking practices by implementing feminist theory.

The approach taken to gather data was a qualitative feminist interviewing process. Findings from this were thematically analysed to produce four key areas of focus: knowledge of spiking, legislation, gendered opinions, and recommendations for change. The compelling findings from this study argue for the introduction of a specific clear and coherent anti-spiking law, to empower victims and give them the confidence to report spiking, providing for better data collection for a more accurate depiction of this societal issue. Alongside new legislation, there is a need for further education and awareness into spiking, to quash the spread of misinformation. Safety will be increased with the implementation of physical measures including CCTV, spiking inhibitors, and increased physical searches to minimise spiking instruments inside venues.

In conclusion, this study provides an insight into perceptions the public have on spiking, its prevalence, and the need for further protection. The gendered lens allowed for a feminist standpoint drawing the difference between gendered attitudes and opinions towards spiking and what can be done to protect women.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

Spiking is a runaway epidemic in contemporary society - a coercive crime that has existed for decades (Home Office,2024). In recent years this crime, and its impacts, has increased exponentially yet still goes unprioritised and marginalised within society. The Home Office (2022) warned that spiking will remain hidden unless more is done to improve awareness and education, and support victims, yet two years later little improvement has been made.

Spiking is described within literature as the 'addition of a substance to an individual non-consensually to cause harm' (Offences Against the Persons Act, 1861; Swan, 2016; Burrell, 2023). Statistics highlight the disproportionate victimisation of females in spiking cases (Home Office,2023; Home Office, 2024). Most recently, spiking was adopted as another contributor to the mass amount of violence committed against women and girls, recognised within the government's 'ENOUGH.' campaign (Home Office, 2024). For decades violence against women and girls has been trivialised and ignored, despite the possibility of anyone becoming the victim of these harrowing crimes, women are repeatedly victimised (Home Office, 2024; Stephenson, 2023). This study uses feminist theory to assess spiking using a gendered influence.

The study was prompted by the researcher's own experiences of spiking, which ignited a passion to explore further the impacts and perceptions of spiking and how the law addresses it, suggesting what can be done to improve this. The researcher wanted to explore whether the lack of knowledge, support, the trivialisation of spiking, and the inadequacy of the law, was a real societal issue.

The focus of this research is to investigate the effectiveness of contemporary legislation and existing anti-spiking practices in protecting women and girls from spiking. It concludes with recommendations on what participants suggest should be implemented to improve this situation. The aims of this research include examining the need for a spiking specific law; analysing public perceptions on current legislation and practises; assessing if there is an existing gap with contemporary spiking legislation; and determining if current law is clear and comprehensive to the public. The aims of this research provide for more insight into how women are impacted by spiking, and probe further the statement that spiking is an issue of violence against women and girls. It provides an insight into perceptions on what might increase safety in the night-time economy, and it highlights the extent of misinformation circulating in society.

The opening section of this dissertation focuses on defining spiking in a social and legal context, exploring legislation and literature surrounding these definitions. This chapter then explores existing literature around three key areas, feminist theory in the context of spiking, existing literature on spiking and finally contemporary legislation and anti-spiking practices and how these affect the prevalence of spiking.

The research methodology adopts a qualitative nature, allowing for opinions and viewpoints to be shared in greater depth and, consequently, satisfying the epistemological and ontological assumptions. Semi-structured feminist interviews are used to gain insight into the perceptions of the sample on a wide area of focus points regarding spiking. Feminist approaches allow for an equal power balance, empowering women when talking about marginalisation and society's neglect of violence against women and girls. Data collected has then been thematically analysed to draw out findings in relation to the research aims.

The final chapter concludes the whole study by assessing if all research aims have been met. It summarises the study's conclusions and proposals, based on responses to the research question. It draws together an assessment of the extent to which legislation and practice protects women and girls from spiking; and proposes recommendations determined from findings and literature on how women and girls can be better protected from this harrowing crime, and what can be done by different parties to support victims and reduce the true extent of spiking.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

This Chapter reviews contemporary literature and legislation regarding spiking, with the aim of assessing the effectiveness of current legislation and anti-spiking practices.

This review has four main areas of focus; the first, definitions of spiking in literature and legislation, what constitutes a spiking offence, and what current data highlights. The second section evaluates the available literature on spiking using feminist theory, to gain a deeper understanding of female experiences of spiking. The third area focusses on spiking in contemporary literature, the impacts of spiking, underreporting and victim blaming influenced by the media. The final focus area examines literary content on current legislation and anti-spiking practice, including the reporting process and the elements of a successful prosecution. Finally, it reviews what practices are currently in place to prevent women and girls from being spiked. The conclusion summarises key literature, highlighting gaps in legal framework and existing literature and stresses the importance of this research, recognising the current limited published research.

2.2 Spiking definitions and context

Having reviewed literature and legislation, it is clear spiking has no single set definition, unlike other offences. Regardless, most literature is consistent with utilising spiking as an umbrella term for the addition of a substance to someone, through drink or injection, without their knowledge or consent, to cause harm or facilitate a secondary crime (Colyer, 2017; Blandamer, 2023; Bendau, 2023; Drinkaware, 2024).

‘Spiking’ does not currently exist as a specific individual offence though. Typically, it is prosecuted by multiple existing pieces of legislation, dependant on context. The law commonly used is the Offences Against the Persons Act 1861, sections 23 and 24, which classifies spiking as administering a noxious, poisonous, or harmful substance to either endanger a life, cause grievous bodily harm (section 23) or injure, aggrieve or annoy (section 24) (Offences Against the Persons Act, 1861). Despite accounts circulating for decades (Colyer, 2017), spiking has recently gained media and political attention as a contemporary societal issue due to a surge in reports of drink spiking and the ‘phenomenon’ of needle spiking (Drinkaware, 2024; Home Office, 2024). Consequently, the Labour Party proposed the introduction of a specific offence during their administration (Labour, 2024).

Although spiking data is elusive, research published focuses on the commonly used substances in spiking and the 'known' prevalence of the issue (Bendau, 2023). Various literature indicates commonly used substances, involving spiking by needle and drink, are 'date rape' drugs, illegal drugs, prescription drugs and alcohol (Blandamer, 2023; Bendau, 2023; Drinkaware, 2023). Despite media misinformation, research asserts alcohol is the most used substance in spiking cases (Greene et al., 2007). Colyer's (2017) research highlights the complexity in validating spiking suspicion, due to rapid metabolism and retrograde amnesia experienced, as clinical analysis is often not executed within the ideal time, consequently failing to validate spiking experiences.

The known prevalence of spiking has continually grown in recent years, with 6,732 spiking incidents reported, of which 957 were needle spiking, in the year ending April 2023 (Home Office, 2024). Despite a long recorded history, the surge in the past 5 years, including the 2021 peak of spiking (Drinkaware, 2024), has caused the present mass public concern and a demand for a government inquiry (Home Office, 2023). A YouGov poll in 2022 revealed that 10% of women in England and Wales have been victim to spiking (Home Office, 2023). Government statistics also posit that the average victim age is 18-21 years old (73% of offences), with 81% of victims being university students (Home Affairs Committee, 2022; Home Office 2023).

Published literature confirms that spiking offences typically happen in public spaces, constituting 80% of all spiking offences (Home Office, 2023). Over half of the reports detail the incident taking place within a bar, followed by a nightclub (Home Office, 2023). Government data illustrates an overall decline in spiking reports since 2021. However, many academics attribute the increased reporting with amplified media attention from campaigning, causing some to conclude that the published data for spiking is only a fraction of what occurs yearly (Bendau, 2023).

2.3 Applied theory in Spiking

Both literature and statistics recognise the disproportionate victimisation of women in spiking. The Home Office's annual report detailed that 74% of all spiking cases in the previous year had been committed against a female (Home Office, 2024). Consequently, it is important to take a gendered lens when reviewing what could be done to better protect victims from spiking.

Feminist theory is concerned with producing connections between gender and crime, where previous schools have lacked in differentiating between genders (Gundy, 2014). Feminist theory takes a feminine standpoint towards crime, considering the direct experiences of women and factors which affect

women when interpreting crime and deviance (Gundy, 2014). It aims to improve the criminal justice system and the way in which female victimisation is understood and managed, considering intersectional differences.

It is beneficial to this research to have a feminist viewpoint as it is concerned with a crime that disproportionately affects women and that has been consistently marginalised; marginalisation which forces an onus on women to protect themselves from harm in the male dominated night-time economy. Women's experiences in the night-time economy are impacted by societal perceptions of their sexual availability for men or the fear of male behaviours. Previous literature on women and the night-time economy has focused on addiction over the repeated victimisation of women (Sheard, 2011), maintaining the limited knowledge of women as victims. The importance of feminist criminology is to highlight the unique female experiences within society, recognising and challenging gender-based violence and the oppression of women. (Jakhmola, 2023).

Research from previous years reflects a similar trend of female victimisation. Essex Police published statistics from 2010 to 2021, before the needle spiking surge, that showed 591 women reported spiking compared to 237 males (Essex Police, 2021). South Yorkshire Police produced similar results over a two-year period, where women were over 3 times more likely the victim of spiking (South Yorkshire Police, 2024). Essex police published data on the perpetrators of spiking, evidencing 74 female perpetrators as opposed to 254 male perpetrators, a 200% increase in male perpetrators of spiking (Essex Police, 2021).

The severity of spiking as a gendered-biased crime has been further recognised following Operation Lester and the adoption of spiking under the governments 'ENOUGH.' campaign (Home Office, 2024). Operation Lester was deployed in 2021 aiming to develop a strategy to manage the spiking surge (Home Office, 2023; Home Office, 2024). Following this, spiking was recognised as a direct issue of violence against women and girls (VAWG) (Home Office, 2024). 'ENOUGH.' is the government campaign employed to tackle and more widely educate society on VAWG (Home Office, 2024).

Although this piece of research focuses on women and girls' experiences of spiking and considers whether they are adequately protected by legislation and practices, statistics highlight that it is not solely women affected by this crime. Men are also at risk, though statistically less, with a YouGov poll showing 5% of men say they have been spiked (Home Office, 2024). Another sector of society disproportionately impacted by spiking is the LGBTQIA+ community, with research showing that they are more likely to be the victim of spiking than heterosexual adults (Drinkaware, 2023), this demonstrates that spiking can affect anyone in contemporary society. However, due to the

disproportionate victimisation of women, and the focus on VAWG as a growing issue, more is needed to protect women.

2.4 Spiking within literature

Despite spiking recorded from the 1800s (Home Office, 2024), there is a dearth of published statistics, and most literature repeats a set of minimal data. The NPCC (National Police Chiefs' Council) corroborates that the true extent of spiking in England and Wales is unknown due to the poor data collection and mass underreporting of this crime (Home Office, 2024). YouGov statistics establish that one in three women have experienced spiking or know someone who has been spiked, with 10% of women being the victim of a spiking incident (Home Office, 2023). The Metropolitan Police saw an increase of 499 cases from the year 2017 to 2019. Following this came the surge in spiking from September 2021 to December 2022, a rise of 1713 cases (Metropolitan Police, 2023). This covered the peak in spiking incidents reported in England and Wales and the advent of needle spiking (Home Office, 2023). However, victims are still eight times more likely to be drink spiked over injection (Drinkaware, 2024).

Spiking can have impacts on victim's physical, mental, and emotional health which can be permanent. The introduction of needles as an instrument of spiking has further added a level of fear around the spreading of blood-borne diseases (Blandamer, 2023; Home Office, 2024). Spiking causes anxiety amongst victims, now unable to return to drinking environments, paranoid of a reoccurrence and obsessive over observation of preventative measures (Home Office Affairs Committee, 2022). Emotional health is similarly impacted due to the shame and embarrassment placed on victim's post offence (Blandamer, 2023; Home Affairs Committee, 2022; Bendau, 2023; Drinkaware, 2024). Due to the nature of spiking, victims may also struggle to process the incident due to substance-induced retrograde amnesia (Blandamer, 2023), which may similarly impact evidence gathering.

The fear of spiking can be deep rooted in women. Research highlights that women's fears are often disproportionate to the reality of being spiked. Consequently, adherence to safety behaviours (including not socialising in certain venues and becoming over cautious) also become disproportionate (Sheard, 2011; Burgess, 2009). Sheard (2011) highlights that the night-time economy is already highly masculinised, with women's experiences being associated with sexual availability and perceived vulnerability to harm. De Crispigny (2001) states women must remain vigilant and self-protect to manage undesired situations with men, taking responsibility for unpleasant action as they optionally visit male dominated areas.

Spiking provokes adoption of protective behaviours, when consuming alcohol, including, not leaving drinks unattended, or buying bottles, not accepting drinks from strangers, and overall reduced alcohol consumption (Burgess, 2009). Website's risk pushing responsibility for incidents onto victims of spiking, when they advise never leave a drink unattended, never accept a drink from someone unknown to you, and limit alcohol consumption. This potentially places responsibility for spiking onto the victim, giving the impression spiking happens because of a failure to take precautions (Drinkaware, 2025).

The media is influential in disseminating fear of spiking. Media outlets highlight a narrative on drug spiking of women in the night-time economy by strangers, despite the prevalence of drug spiking being substantially lower than alcohol spiking. They push stories of drug-facilitated sexual assault, which cause women to fear not only spiking but the horrifying consequences that could follow (Sheard, 2011). Despite this, Hamner rationalises an overall fear of spiking as reasonable, given the routine nature of violence against women in society (Hamner,1987; Sheard, 2011), along with an overwhelming fear of men in the night-time economy. Research highlights the effect media representation of spiking has on women's fears, with the reproduction of harmful myths and victim blaming embedded in spiking media, further normalising these issues within societal attitudes (Vale Pires, 2024).

Published data is only a fraction of what takes place. Many cases go unreported and unsupported. Research by Angela Ruskin University found that only 1 in 10 spiking incidents are reported to police (Drinkaware, 2022). Underreporting seems to stem from the fact that victims fear little justice will result from reporting their experiences; half of those who did not report claimed it was a result of seeing little point in doing so (Busardó, 2019; Home Affairs Committee,2022; Bendau, 2023). Issues of shame, insecurity, and fear of not being believed led to a quarter of all women not notifying anyone that they had been spiked (Drinkaware, 2024).

Many women find it difficult to share their experiences of spiking, and seek support, due to the normalised nature of victim blaming. Victim blaming is evident in most areas of VAWG, including rape and sexual assault, where misinformation about women's behaviour has somewhat normalised this crime (Rape Crisis, 2025). Unfortunately, these attitudes are also carried over into spiking. Victims are typically made to experience embarrassment and shame for what has happened to them and blamed for contributing to their own victimisation (Stephenson, 2023). Raise your voice highlighted common barriers to reporting spiking, including fear of not being believed, a feeling of shame, confusion around the law and a fear of the consequences they face (Raise your voice, 2022; Home Affairs Committee,2022; Home Office, 2024).

This attitude of placing responsibility on the victim, and a general neglect for victims, stems from a lack of education and awareness on spiking. Misogyny also facilitates this disregard for victims as males' distance themselves from incidents of spiking, unlike women, where research highlights, they tend to keep the spiking discourse alive (Sheard, 2011). Research has also highlighted the neglect from door staff in the night-time economy, with women being afraid to ask for help due to previous or expected negative interactions. (Burgess, 2009).

Another area where societal education fails to address the reality of the night-time economy relates to effectively identifying spiking. With signs of spiking and excessive alcohol consumption being similar, many women are disregarded as drunk when spiked (Colyer, 2017). Both share symptoms including nausea, confusion, slurred speech, visual problems (Medway Council, 2025; Metropolitan Police, 2025). Many women believe that without a secondary offence taking place, spiking alone does not justify reporting (Home Office, 2024). Female spiking experiences are repeatedly marginalised, even when a victim is confident enough to report it, with barriers including not knowing how or who to report an incident to (Home Office, 2024). The complexity of providing evidence of spiking and the resulting limited convictions provide a further barrier to reporting.

2.5 Current legislation

There is currently no legislation specifically addressing 'spiking' as we currently understand it. Instead, it is prosecuted by multiple pieces of legislation dependant on the context of the incident and whether a secondary offence has been committed. The most used legislation to prosecute spiking offences is the Offences Against the Persons Act 1861, sections 23 and 24 (Home Office, 2024). If a victim reports a spiking incident to police, four questions are considered: What happened? Where did it happen? When did it happen? And who did it? A victim will then be asked to provide toxicology samples. Issues surrounding this are not only the near impossibility of identifying a suspect in clubs and bars, but victims may be unaware of their victimisation. Many spiking incidents also involve rapid metabolising substances (Home Office, 2024), Westmarland (2024) Highlighted a lack of timely forensic evidence collection by police and healthcare providers which can further complicate a successful charge.

A victim must provide evidence of a suspect, substance, and impact as a minimum for a spiking charge. Most drugs used in spiking incidents are metabolised quickly, some within 12 hours and, although police stress the importance of toxicology tests, many women are not aware of the time limitation to testing. This makes providing evidence of a suspect and the substance used incredibly challenging for the victim. NPCC published results highlighting only 12.5% of spiking victims were able to identify a suspect and,

of those 378 cases in total, only 4 ended up with a conviction (Home Office, 2024). On this point, there is limited data available on previous conviction rates for spiking.

As spiking offences are not recorded under an individual offence, data on the prevalence of the issue remains difficult to gather. The fact that multiple laws are used to prosecute spiking currently (Home Office, 2024), adds to the complexity of analysing data on spiking offences.

The Home Affairs Committee published a report (2022) which recommended government action to prevent spiking. This specified a 'victim-centred approach' to dealing with spiking, moving most 'date rape' drugs from a class C to a class B classification, a move aimed at deterring perpetrators from carrying them. The Home Office declared the need for collaboration amongst police forces to ensure consistent reporting and the addition of spiking related questions on the national crime survey to collect more detail on spiking incidents.

Many published documents conclude that the current laws covering spiking are effective for few spiking offences, and gaps are identified. Government research highlights the benefits of introducing a specific spiking law (Home Office, 2024). Despite the common perception amongst most that spiking is illegal, a study by the Home Office found most were unaware of laws covering spiking, and that alcohol is a facilitator to spiking (Home Office, 2024).

A specific law would remove archaic language, ensuring it is more accessible to the public and fit for purpose, resulting in increased reporting and confidence in legislation (Home Office, 2024; Home Affairs Committee, 2022; Hansard, 2023). A specific law would ensure more comprehensive data collection from police services, allowing for a more accurate depiction of its prevalence (Home Affairs Committee, 2022). A more wide-scale and better understanding of the law would also further deter perpetrators by clarifying the illegality of the act (Home Office, 2024).

Currently, there is no mandatory anti-spiking practices or regulation in venues in England and Wales. A commonly implemented practice is the 'Ask for Angela' scheme existing to support individuals who feel uncomfortable in social venues (Ask for Angela, 2022). However, an issue with this, in relation to spiking, is that one may not perceive harm before it is carried out. Combined with poor training, for staff, recently the subject of a BBC investigation, this potentially leads an ineffectiveness, (and lack of awareness), of this scheme for spiking victims (BBC News, 2024), yet this is the only investigation carried out and one of a limited nature, so may not be generalisable to every venue.

In conclusion, this chapter summarises all available literature and statistics on spiking, arguably minimal as it is. It focuses on the importance of a gendered view on spiking and VAWG and the impacts on them. It summarises information published on the consequences of spiking and women's fears in the night-time economy. It also covers the issue of underreporting and victim blaming being normalised in contemporary society, focusing on masculinity and criminal justice attitudes towards women as victims of spiking.

Lastly, it focuses on the existing legislation that cover spiking and the difficulties in securing a successful prosecution, highlighting complexities and gaps within legislation, emphasising the need for a specific spiking law, it spotlights the absence of legal requirements and anti-spiking practices to minimise spiking in venues and a need for these to be implemented effectively. This was a 2024 Labour Party manifesto commitment.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter provides an overview of how data was gathered and analysed to collect public perception on spiking legislation and anti-spiking practices. It details the methodological approaches considered designing this study and justifies their benefit within this research. It covers the approaches, research methods, sampling strategy, and the pros and cons with each.

The latter half of this chapter explores the process of data collection and details how data was analysed and what this achieved. Finally, this chapter highlights the ethical issues potentially inherent in this type of research, and evidence how these were overcome during this study.

3.2 Methodological approach

The ontological assumption of this research is one of a constructivism view. This research focuses on reality constructed through individuals' interactions, perceptions, and experiences. It highlights the significance placed on individuals' experiences in explaining views on reality (Bryman, 2021). The main ontological approach allows for consideration of gendered dynamics and the impact they have on experiencing reality (Bryman, 2021).

The epistemological assumption of this research is of an interpretivist approach. This research reflects the ideology that behaviours are interpreted within the context of individual experiences, stressing the importance of understanding from those who have experienced the issue (Bryman, 2021).

Considering the theoretical assumptions, the most suitable research approach is one of a qualitative nature. The benefits of carrying out a qualitative approach are to produce a deeper understanding of how the social world is experienced from different perspectives, attributing meaning to all interactions and a personal insight into individual experiences (Bryman, 2021). Qualitative research allows for context to be considered with purpose; it provides insight into decision making and reasoning behind responses. Despite some flaws, a qualitative approach is best suited to this research with its focus on meeting the abovementioned assumptions and focusing on personal experience and social interaction influencing perceptions.

3.3 Research design

This study adopts a qualitative research approach, employing semi-structured interviews. Those semi-structured interviews draw from an interview guide allowing for a more informal style of information gathering (Adeoye-Olatunde, 2021). The interview guide allows for flexibility around questions, whilst producing responses to key areas from all participants, and gaining any potential unanticipated or unelicited findings with interview prompts (Bryman, 2021).

This research study involves an interactional exchange of dialogue to gain insight into public perceptions of spiking policy and anti-spiking practice (Bryman, 2021). Semi-structured interviews allow for the ontological assumption to be met as participants' knowledge, understanding, and interactions impact perceptions around spiking (Mason, 2018). The benefit of qualitative interviews is they produce data surrounding societal perceptions in depth which various other qualitative methods would not. One limitation of qualitative interviews is time consumption and the creation of a power imbalance between researcher and participant, which may impact data collection (Mason, 2018).

A feminist interview approach is taken within this research to minimise the effect of an unequal power dynamic. Feminist interviews allow for an equal gender, and researcher to participant, relationship by allowing participants to have a level of control over the interview, including the ability to ask the researcher questions, refuse questions and the use of prompts (Flick, 2023). They allow for subjective experiences and views which inform opinions to be validated (Roberts, 1981), especially for women who are disproportionately impacted by spiking and its repercussions.

The sampling method applied within this study was convenience sampling. The desired target population in this study was up to 11 participants of a mixed gender, between the ages of 18 to 25 – to reflect the age group most victimised by spiking (Home Office, 2023). Convenience sampling allowed for participants to be gathered from peer groups and those nearby allowing for simple and accessible information-gathering. More importantly, it allowed for caution when selecting participants ensuring they had not been victimised by spiking which would have caused ethical problems (Etikan, 2015). A recruitment poster was used to provide essential information, including research aims, essential requirements of participants, and existing support.

Convenience sampling is beneficial to this study due to constrained time, meeting the requirements of the target population, and accessibility to participants (Golzar et al., 2022). A drawback of this sampling strategy is sampling bias in selecting participants to produce desired results, and inaccurate

representation of the wider population (Golzar et al., 2022). To overcome this a varied selection of ages within the parameters were chosen and an equal representation of genders. In addition, such generalisation issues are overcome using existing literature alongside these research findings.

3.4 Data collection and analysis

Qualitative data produced from this study was collected through semi-structured interviews with chosen participants. When all participants were gathered and consent provided, hour interview slots were allocated via university email, through Microsoft teams, to allow for data protection. Interviews were held over Microsoft teams at a time suitable for the participant ensuring high engagement, comfort, and convenience for participant and researcher (Sedgwick & Spiers, 2009). Once interviews had commenced participants were reminded of the aims of this research, given information on the researcher, and reassured that all answers were beneficial, to provide a comforting and empowering atmosphere for the participant (Herron, 2022). Alongside this, participants were provided with the opportunity to introduce themselves, reminded of their rights to withdraw and, finally, consent for recording was attained.

Participants were read questions from the interview guide with time to think and respond, sometimes prompted by the researcher to expand on specific opinions and viewpoints. Penultimately, participants were given the opportunity to ask the researcher any questions in relation to the research topic and data. Finally, once all questions were answered, participants were asked to provide a pseudonym by which they would be referred to throughout the research for anonymity and privacy purposes (Wang,2024). Once all data was collected and recorded via Microsoft Teams it was transcribed.

All data was correctly transcribed, reviewed and then analysed to identify key patterns and opinions in relation to the research aims. Given the qualitative nature of the study, interviews were analysed using a process of thematic analysis. Transcripts from the interviews were reviewed noting specific reoccurring themes, opinions, and trends in phrasing (Bryman, 2021). From this analysis four key themes were created: knowledge of spiking; legislation; gendered opinions; and participant responses . These were identified from repeated responses and shared opinions and in some cases uncommon and unexpected views on spiking. Each identified theme contained three to five subthemes identified through interpretation of patterns in response to set questions (Braun & Clarke,2022).

The benefit of thematic analysis for this qualitative study is it provides flexibility in interpretation of public opinion on spiking legislation and policy through discourse from the interviews. It allows the

methodological assumptions to be considered when analysing data, allowing for research questions to be answered directly through experience and knowledge gained in society (Willig & Stainton-Rogers, 2017).

On reflection, despite the overarching benefits of conducting qualitative studies online via Microsoft Teams, technological issues arose. The complexity surrounding the software provided challenges initially and connectivity issues meant various transcripts had gaps and areas of ambiguity (Irani, 2018), however with time these issues were overcome and corrected to ensure accurate data collection and interpretation of participant responses.

3.5 Ethical considerations

Prior to the research being conducted, it received ethical approval from Leeds Beckett Local Research Ethics Committee (LREC). Despite being deemed risk category three it fulfilled all the requirements for it to be carried out safely and ethically. Ethical issues that were considered were informed consent, avoidance of harm, avoidance of intrusion and privacy, deception, and the power imbalance.

To overcome issues regarding informed consent and deception participants were provided with an information sheet prior to the interview. This gave in depth detail of the aims of the study, what participants would be required to do and information on data protection and confidentiality. Participants then signed a consent form. By providing participants with the purpose of the interviews and research aims, it allows participants to consent to all aspects of the research without deception (Bryman, 2021). Furthermore, participants were given the right to withdraw at the time of the interview with no repercussions and the right to withdraw up to March the 1st 2025, four weeks after the interviews, (Mason, 2018).

Research into spiking must be carried out sensitively and minimise harm throughout to participants and researchers. To ensure this set requirements were detailed in the participant information sheet and poster, including excluding any participant if previously victimised by spiking.

If harm or distress was caused by subjects mentioned in interviews, details of university and charity support services were provided. Participants were also given an opportunity to pause, postpone, and skip questions within the interview process if they felt uncomfortable, although questions were created to minimise distress and harm. Although not called upon, interview procedure would have involved referring participants to support, if needed.

As a result of the own researcher's experiences of spiking, the same elements of safeguarding were applied, including the right to pause, terminate the interview and take rest breaks during research. Leeds Beckett University support services were also available to provide support if needed, with an aim of minimising any further harm. The ability to carry out the research without causing harm to the researcher was assessed by supervisors of the project and LREC, ensuring the study was carried out safely (Bryman, 2021).

Participants remained fully aware of study details, to maintain confidentiality and confidence in anonymity. In addition, post interview all participants had to provide a pseudonym which they would be referred to by within this study to protect their identity (Wang, 2024). Using the participant information sheet and consent form participants were informed of data protection and storage information, audio files were deleted after transcription, and no audio was shared. Comprehensive, transparent, and accurate information, prior to the interviews, met ethical obligation to ensure no deception (Bryman, 2021).

The final ethical consideration related to overcoming a power imbalance. By taking a feminist approach to qualitative research, an equal power dynamic between genders, and researcher to participant, was established. With the subject of this research one of gendered sensitivity it allowed for the empowerment of participant responses and confidence in sharing experiences and opinions (Flick, 2023). This method of qualitative interviewing ensures informed consent without pressure on participants, maximising comfort, confidence, and safety (Mason, 2018).

3.6 Conclusion

A qualitative research approach was adopted for this study as it best fit with the research aims and methodological assumptions which helped fill research gaps within the discourse of spiking. This research benefits from the use of semi-structured interviews with up to 11 participants to gather various insights into spiking perceptions whilst allowing a flexible structure. An emphasis on a gendered lens is taken with feminist methods applied throughout the study, to allow for an equal power balance, empowering both genders throughout the process, with specific reference to the fact women are not only disproportionately affected by this crime but also that crimes against them are typically marginalised.

Thematic analysis is beneficial to this research study as it allows repetitive patterns and behaviours to be highlighted and discussed, upholding the theoretical assumptions of this research, and allowing for insight into perception of reality.

Ethical issues that arose when designing the study were limited by implementing strategies and precautions throughout the study's design and conduct, to avoid harm to the participants and the researcher. This resulted in providing the most detail-rich responses, ethically, in relation to the research aims.

Chapter 4: Findings and Discussions

4.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the research findings in relation to public perceptions of legislation and anti-spiking practice. The key themes discussed in this chapter are public knowledge, legislative changes, gendered opinions, and responses. Within these themes, subsections are discussed. Knowledge surrounding spiking covers frequency of discussion, defining spiking and prevalence. Legislative changes explore knowledge of existing legislation, suitability of legal definitions, clarity, understanding and modernity of legislation. The theme gendered opinions investigate differing attitudes across gender including masculinity, victim-blaming, and fear. The final theme, which contains respondents' recommendations, details suggested pre-emptive measures, legislative amendments and education and awareness programmes. Throughout this chapter, themes are compared with the existing literature forementioned in the literature review, to assess if findings corroborate previous limited research. Finally, this chapter concludes by summing up all themes discovered.

4.2 Spiking knowledge

The first section of the interviews examined the level of existing knowledge on spiking. Discussions revealed that despite minimal published research, people are superficially aware of spiking and what it entails. Referring to discussing spiking among friends there was a clear gender divide in the frequency and detail conveyed. Analysis showed that female participants more frequently heard and conversed about spiking, with many suggesting this correlated with internalised fear.

“I talk about it quite a lot to be honest. A lot of people I know have been spiked” –
Jessica.

“It is something I will hear about probably five or six times a week” – Petal.

Conversely, male participants emphasised the rarity at which spiking is discussed, with one participant stating the only reason it would be talked about is if someone within their circle was directly affected.

“I do not think me, or my friends talk about it, unless someone we know has been spiked” – John.

However, a similarity between both genders was the source of their knowledge of spiking. Most participants acknowledged social media and dramatised television shows, or experiences of known victims. None of the respondents attributed their knowledge and understanding to an educational source.

“I do not know anything educational really” – Alexander.

These findings corroborate published research, that portrays how spiking affects the genders differently, with women keeping the discourse of spiking awareness alive through mutual discussion. Sheard (2011) explored the relationship between women’s catastrophising fears of spiking and probability of victimisation, finding most women adapt and change behaviours to mitigate victimisation, impacting their own experiences of the night-time economy. Burgess et al. (2009) found that women share stories and information about spiking due to high levels of fear surrounding the issue (Bendau,2023; Dorandeu, 2006). The findings of this study suggest little has changed since Burgess et al. (2009)’s findings.

Findings further exhibited that participants were informed about methods of spiking, with most defining spiking as substances added to drinks, the most common form of spiking (Drinkaware, 2024). When probed for any other prevalent examples of spiking, all participants except one identified spiking via injections as the second most common, which is reflected in statistics.

“Skin to needle contact, most commonly it is through putting something in someone’s drink” – Eve.

On the other hand, participants had less knowledge of substances, with most simply identifying “drugs” in general. Only one participant was able to identify examples of what may be used when spiking.

“Ketamine has been used before...Rohypnol has also been used” – Miguel.

Participant failed to commonly identify alcohol as a substance used to spike, asserting that it would only be spiking if the alcohol was administered to someone not consuming any alcohol. A common misconception highlighted drugs used for spiking are those of a powder or tablet form leaving ambiguity regarding alcohol, with many failing to recognise that alcohol facilitated spiking too. This emphasises the gap in knowledge regarding what is used when spiking, with alcohol being identified through

toxicology research as the leading substance (Bendau, 2023; Blandamer, 2023; Greene et al., 2007). This not only identifies a gap in knowledge but also contributes to dangerous misinformation.

Spiking was recognised as a frequent societal issue by all participants, who emphasised the prevalence of spiking, especially at university. Many participants constructed statistics to display this:

“One in three people being spiked” - Jessica.

“One in every five club attendees” - Alexander.

Although these statistics are not based on published data, they reflect participant’s perceived levels of spiking. Older respondents, who may have been socialising at the time, asserted that spiking is just as common now as the needle spiking outbreak in 2021-22. Nevertheless, it is not receiving the same publicity, implying it is perceived less of an issue. Participants stressed that spiking happens daily and with increasing frequency. Media coverage and public statistics no longer present the increasing prevalence of spiking, whilst the reality suggested by anecdotal evidence is of an alarming increase (Bendau, 2023; Blandamer, 2023; Sheard; 2011).

“It is very common. I reckon it is still growing as well” - Rose.

The research identified a consensus that women were more often the victims of spiking. All participants also identified this disproportionate victimisation and the surface-level impact of spiking. Respondents pinpointed women and girls, typically students, as most likely to experience spiking. These claims were based on personal encounters, media stories and television.

“I would imagine females are targeted more and probably university age, 18-20 years old sort of” – Jessica.

Only four of the eleven participants acknowledged spiking can happen to anyone. However, all participants identified the disproportionate impact on women, suggesting recognition of a crime that majorly affects women, which data confirms (Dorondeu, 2004; Hansard, 2023; Drinkaware, 2024; Home Office, 2024). Despite public recognition that spiking primarily affects women not enough is done to minimise this.

“I would say women, women definitely get spiked more” – Crisp.

Participants who mentioned the impacts of spiking produced little detail, likely due to a general lack of knowledge on how spiking can impact mental health, physical health, risks of blood borne disease (with use of needles), all of which contribute to the trauma of this offence (Blandamer, 2023; Home Affairs Committee, 2022, Home Office, 2023). Instead, many generalised the impacts caused by spiking as non-specifically harmful.

“You are putting people’s lives at risk; they are not going out to get spiked” – Finn.

This theme highlights participants are aware of what spiking is, although often had less knowledge of the substances used in spiking. Women were recognised as the most likely victims of the crime, although how women were impacted by spiking remained vague, despite participants often suggesting they were aware of people who had been spiked. This demonstrates a gap between awareness of spiking and understanding of its impacts on victims, which are only really understood when someone is associated with spiking directly.

The deficiency of information on spiking may provide further difficulty in the public’s understanding of what constitutes spiking. The key aspects predominantly mentioned by all participants were: a substance additionally added, mostly in the context of a drink, which may cause harm or negative impact, with an emphasis on it done so without the victim’s knowledge.

“A foreign substance being placed into someone’s drink, without the other person being aware of it” – Sid.

Despite many not directly mentioning consent it is implied in most participants’ definitions of spiking, with reference to it being done without the victim’s knowledge, cooperation, or engagement. Respondents also reflected on the unwilling and unwitting consequences on the victim, including the loss of control, being taken advantage of, and illness.

4.3 Current legislation

The second theme that was explored related to an understanding of current spiking legislation. Overall, participants had limited knowledge of specific legislation and practices related to spiking, with levels of knowledge varying from no knowledge at all, to an assumption it must be illegal although respondents were unsure under what law(s). Only one of the eleven participants was aware of spiking being covered by varied legislation (although unsure of which ones).

“No, I know it is probably illegal, but I do not know anything specific” – Jessica.

“I did not know there was any laws for it” – Finn.

The overall absence of knowledge around existing legislation underlines two key concerns related to both whether the law is easily accessible and understood by the public, due to a lack of specific spiking terminology (Hansard, 2023). Without the deterrent effect a well-established offence provides, perpetrators remain confident in spiking and victims are likewise not encouraged to report any offence. Both further transmit the false narrative that without a secondary offence there is no incentive to report spiking (Westmarland, 2025).

When participants were shown the current legislation that covers spiking incidents, what was striking from the findings was the overall lack of clarity and understanding. Initially all participants claimed they understood, but respondents became less certain as the legislation was discussed. The main terminology of S23 and S24 are ‘noxious, destructive and poisonous’ (Offences Against the Persons Act, 1861), and when questioned about what these may include, many participants paused and provided little detail. The overall trend captured was high class drugs and poisons, with little reference to alcohol.

“Threatening things” -Alexander.

Many participants suggested the words used in the legislation were overly complicated. When this was further explored, many participants revised their previous opinions on the 1861 act arguing the wording was unclear and did not capture the true nature of spiking.

“It uses umbrella terms... instead of explicitly saying Spiking” – Miguel.

Additionally, despite alcohol being the most used substance, only a quarter of participants felt the law, as drafted, included alcohol, because of the lack of specific inclusion in the text. Subsequently, they believed over-serving of alcohol was not spiking, or reluctantly accepted its inclusion, albeit with the qualification of it being ‘technically’ included.

“I do not know, no one really sees alcohol as a poison anymore” – Alexander.

“(Over pouring alcohol) Yes, if the person wasn’t drinking” - Stitch

Few felt being over-served alcohol at a bar could be viewed as spiking, with the bar servers having a legal responsibility to serve in accordance with the law. In contrast, 50% of participants did not believe a friend over-serving alcohol was spiking, with one participant suggesting it would be spiking only if there was an intent to harm. This lack of clarity on alcohol as a spiking agent is not only dangerous but subject of a widespread myth too, as media outlets push the narrative that spiking is only carried out by strangers using tablets, something which is not the reality at all (Sheard, 2011).

Alongside arguing that the legislation covering spiking is unclear, all participants unanimously agreed that the current legislation covering spiking (OAPA, 1861), was too outdated to cover modern day spiking, with little coverage of modern spiking methods, no direct use of modern terminology, and a failure to identify the excessive harm to women and girls.

“No... 150 years was a long time ago; current laws just avoid spiking” – Miguel.

“Because of how it has grown and the different kinds of spiking that happen now, I do not think it is effective to stop it or help it” – Rose.

One of the complications caused by this outdated law, including the use of archaic language, is producing barriers to reporting. This is a result of not using the terminology of modern spiking, resulting in victims understanding being limited and them not recognising their own experiences of spiking as an offence (UK Parliament, 2022; Home Office, 2025). Consistently, spiking offences are parcelled up with secondary offences, including offences against the person, sexual assault and more (Home Office, 2024). Whilst this could be appropriate for some victims in some cases, for those simply spiked with no secondary offence it causes complexity.

This theme highlights the inadequacy of current legislation as, although participants could demonstrate an understanding of how spiking is defined, this was not due to clarity of the legislation but instead informal information sharing. In all cases, participants felt legislation was not only unclear but outdated.

4.4 Gendered Views

Arguably one of the most striking observations evident in analysis of the data was the embedded gendered opinions within participant responses. These were apparent throughout the interviews. This proved beneficial to this research as it investigates the general public’s gendered influence on spiking and how gender impacts experiences.

Many answers from male participants suggested a disregard for spiking victims or a general distancing from the offence, with the presumption it does not affect them in the same capacity it affects women. A minority of male participants explicitly said that they do not typically talk about spiking as it does not affect them and demonstrated a limited view.

“I do not really talk about it a lot as it is not something that directly impacts me” – Sid.

“Because if you get spiked, you are not necessarily in danger so to speak... but it does have long term affects if you get spiked and raped” – Alexander.

The first quote displays a general male distancing from spiking as an issue because of the disproportionate victimisation of females. Therefore, it is not something men have to continuously worry about. As Sheard (2011) opposed, it stays at the forefront of women’s minds when in the night-time economy.

The second quote exhibits a male disregard for spiking as a singular offence and pushes further the myth that spiking without a secondary offence is not worth the same public censure, despite secondary offences only occurring in 16% of spiking cases (Home Office, 2024). These views further silence victims and contribute to mass under reporting of the crime. They portray the masculine attitude that is familiarly taken towards violence against women and girls, where the issue is trivialised. Masculine attitudes act as an inhibitor to empathising with the violence women are facing in contemporary society.

“It is common in a big group of boys for it to be joked about” – Miguel.

This quote highlights the critical issue of violence against women and girls consistently being downplayed and ignored. The way in which VAWG is joked about reflects deeper societal issues on the normalisation of violence against women and the minimalization of women’s trauma. Trivialising this issue shows the gendered disregard for the safety of women.

Interview responses exhibited a trend of fear of spiking victimisation, exclusively presented by female participants. These participants also contributed pre-emptive and mitigating measures they have adopted when out, their own anecdotes of spiking and the consistent need for caution.

“It is sad we have to be cautious; you can’t really enjoy yourself to the full extent” – Eve.

“We have had to buy cup covers and cover our drinks” – Crisp.

These female participants reflect the wider thought processes in most women in relation to spiking, e.g., the constant need for caution, fear of victimisation, and the limiting impact the need for safety has on enjoyment. Sheard (2011) highlights that the likelihood of women being spiked is often not proportionate to the cautious behaviours women develop. Most women develop these behaviours to reduce victimisation, including consuming drinks quicker, limiting alcohol consumption and remaining as a group. Women have an imprinted fear of spiking due to the unequal victimisation of women and the further harm it poses in the already ‘dangerous’ masculinised night-time economy (Brooks, 2011; Burgess et al., 2009).

Misogynistic preconceptions, alongside a disregard for women’s experiences, can lead into a further gendered issue of victim blaming. Victim blaming can take various forms in relation to spiking, including questioning where drinks are left, who with, and a lack of precautionary behaviours (Stephenson, 2023). Just over a quarter of the participants gave responses that alluded to victim blaming, suggesting victims did not prevent spiking or that spiking could be caused by inexperience in the night-time economy. Victim blaming responses were contributed by both male and female participants, but males exhibited this to a greater extent.

“Don’t let randomers buy you drinks” – Petal.

“Victims can do stuff to prevent themselves from being in that position” – Miguel.

Victim blaming is constantly embedded within spiking discourse, and often factored into people’s individual perception of spiking victims and the reasons behind the crime. Victim blaming is seen in many cases of violence against women and is a leading contributor to why victims do not report these crimes (Bolton et al., 2023). It involves placing the responsibility for the offence on the victim, implying their behaviour was careless, foolish, or a contributory factor to the offence, rather than blaming the perpetrator (Raise your voice, 2022). This victim blaming narrative is further pushed by a focus of victim behaviours in research (Sheard, 2011), hostile medical attention following an offence, and sexist media coverage of these crimes deliberately focusing on what women are perceived to be doing to contribute to their victimisation including ‘risky behaviours’ (Stephenson, 2023). These attitudes prompt women to feel ashamed, embarrassed and at fault (Blandamer, 2023; Bendau, 2023; Drinkaware, 2024).

4.5 Responses and changes

The final theme of the interview analysis focussed on suggestions to improve safety for women and girls. These are categorised into three sections: physical interventions, education and awareness, and legislation. What emerged from the responses were that current anti-spiking practices in place either only existed for a set amount of time or were not done adequately. Participants referred to the short-lived introduction of cup covers following the 2021-22 period of increased spiking, a measure which is effective in deterring drink spiking, but not needle spiking which emerged at the same time.

“Clubs were giving cup covers and stuff, so maybe trying to re-enforce that again” –
Stitch.

“Security measures like cameras, they need to be able to see everything in the club”
– Alexander.

Participants believed cup covers would not only further protect people from spiking but also reduce fear of drink spiking. Although it was mentioned less, participants discussed the need for CCTV in bars and clubs not only to act as a deterrent to potential spikers, but to aid identification of an offender in reporting the crime to police.

The reporting process for a spiking incident is typically a barrier to women reporting, as the threshold requirements for a successful charge are onerous (Home Office, 2024). The installation of security cameras and CCTV could help with these requirements as the identification of perpetrators may be made easier for victims and police.

An overwhelming majority of interviewees felt that if door searches were carried out more, and to a better standard, they would feel much safer and spiking cases would decrease. One participant highlighted the comparison between male and female searches, emphasising that it is inadequate: women have their bags searched and men are simply patted down, meaning instruments and substances used to spike can easily go concealed.

“Maybe they should get you to empty all pockets...because the amount of times people get little bags [drugs] in is too often” – Finn

“Being searched meticulously as you go into clubs, because like a needle should be pretty easy to identify on a person”- Stitch.

This highlights the need for more intensive searches which would help prevent spiking offences by restricting people carrying substances and needles into venues. It would also provide women with more confidence, and greater safety, when in the night-time economy.

4.6 Education and awareness

In addition, participants emphasised the need for increased education and awareness around all aspects of spiking. This included education on the signs and symptoms of spiking, safety precautions, and what to do if spiked. This research accentuates a lack of awareness of spiking in relation to laws, substances, and common misconceptions.

All participants emphasised the importance of education and awareness around spiking including through teaching, social media campaigns and news coverage on incidents.

“To make people understand there needs to be more education around it, I think”
– Petal.

“Promoting it on social media and stuff, which I think is growing more and more” –
Finn.

Wider and increased awareness and education about spiking, signs of spiking and the impacts on victims, will encourage reporting. (Home Affairs Committee, 2022). Further, public disapproval of spiking and the removal of victim blaming could help act as an increased deterrent to perpetrators, as awareness of the consequent punishment is enhanced. However, attitudes towards VAWG, generally, will need altering to bring about societal disapproval of the crime.

“In pubs and stuff, you see things saying that drugs are prohibited and things like that, making it more well-known it is not allowed- Miguel.

Additionally, participants felt door staff needed more training and support in relation to spiking. Not only was the requirement for more door staff made, but female participants contended that door staff in instances of spiking can be hostile and harsh.

“Security can sometimes be nicer when it happens”- Eve.

“They need to make sure everyone is safe” – Eve.

Participants suggested that door staff fail to distinguish between self-induced intoxication and spiking. This provokes an unsympathetic, even harmful, reaction to spiking victims, further reinforcing the narrative of victim blaming, compounded by the belief that intoxication is solely the individual’s responsibility (Stephenson, 2023). Bendau (2023) found spiking victims may not seek medical and professional help due to the stigma experienced from medical professionals and police officers post offence (Busardò, 2019; Blandamer, 2023). Albeit, training of door staff alone will not resolve this issue, the correct treatment of victims will result in more women feeling safer if victimised and seeking adequate support after the initial incident.

4.7 Legislative changes

The final theme related to reducing spiking which emerged in interview responses was amendment of legislation and the creation of a specific spiking offence. All participant responses detailed a need for a legislative change covering spiking to better aid victims, improve awareness and deter perpetrators.

“Different laws put in place, like specifically for spiking... with a threat of a certain amount of years doing it” – Sid.

“It would not be a PR stunt, but it would make national news and it would make spiking in the headlines... helping raise awareness” – Miguel.

The Labour Party (2024) proposed the introduction of a specific spiking law, to aid criminal justice responses to incidents. The new spiking legislation would correct and raise the media profile of spiking, attention, better support victims and Labour argues, would lead to increased levels of reporting due to increased confidence in, and understanding of, the law (Home Office, 2024).

Perpetrators would be sent a clear message that spiking is not tolerated by the public and government, and the perception that spiking might be illegal will become definite (Hansard, 2023), with associated clear tariffs for punishment. The night-time economy will become a safer space for women and girls (Hansard, 2023).

To summarise this chapter, participants responses created four main areas of interest. Firstly, the cohort’s knowledge of legislation relating to spiking was weak, and of further worry was the limited

understanding of the legislation. Many participants were unaware of alcohol as a spiking substance, reflecting a widely accepted misconception amongst society. Overall definitions demonstrated a superficial knowledge of what spiking is, but without reference to the legislation. This evidenced a need for legislations to change.

Participants overall knowledge of spiking, in terms of substances and methods, was limited. Participants were not aware of what is commonly used, and some only aware of a singular method of spiking. Few participants vocalised the traumatic impact spiking has on an individual, even though they felt aware of how serious of an issue it is, and the frequency at which it is happening.

Gendered victimisation was identified by all participants, recognising women were at the centre of this crime. Some awareness was reflected in how often spiking was spoken about by participants, typically amongst females. Participants created gendered differences through opinions of spiking. This theme identified that masculinity was an inhibitor of understanding the severity of spiking and the impact which it has on women. Victim blaming was apparent in both male and female respondents, stemming from misconceptions about spiking and masculinity. Female participants highlighted the impact that the fear of spiking has had on their experience of the night-time economy.

Finally, participants agreed recommendations that would decrease spiking and make the night-time economy safer for women and girls. These included physical measures, increased education and awareness, and legislative changes. All participant evidenced their disapproval for spiking and the desperate need for spiking to be taken seriously.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

This research investigated the effectiveness of current legislation and anti-spiking practices in protecting women and girls from spiking and highlighted a failure to successfully achieve this. It confirmed that the researchers' original concerns about public attitudes towards spiking remain a rooted societal issue.

Key gaps detected within current spiking literature and legislation include minimal contemporary research into the experiences of women, including very little considering gendered influences, resulting in an inadequate account of how it impacts them. There is a noticeable gap in modern legislation and sanctions for spiking. Most importantly, there is a scarcity of resources and practices available to further protect women from spiking in the night-time economy. The absence of a spiking specific law contributes to mass under-reporting, limited data collection and limited support. The extreme deficiency in published research into various aspects of spiking led to the repeated reliance on set sources through this project.

Despite, some published research into women's experiences of spiking these findings have not been reflected truly within legislation and practices to protect against spiking. This is a result despite the case of years of trivialisation and marginalisation of the crime. 'ENOUGH' the government scheme to help reduce this epidemic of accepted VAWG was only founded in 2022 (Gov, 2022), spiking was only incorporated into phase two in March 2023 (Home Office, 2024) despite a history of spiking affecting women.

Adopting a qualitative approach aligned with the epistemological and ontological assumptions of the study, stressing the importance of experience and society in shaping perceptions, delivers a way of seeing the spiking phenomenon from those who hear and experience it most. This governed the participant selection.

Qualitative semi-structured interviews were adopted to allow for an informal method of data gathering. A feminist interviewing approach allowed for empowerment of women's voices and creation of an equal power dynamic. This allowed for confidence and comfort during interviews to encourage a deeper insight into spiking. Data gathered via these interviews was thematically analysed, investigating significant patterns and trends, highlighting gaps in legislation, gendered opinions, and societal

understanding. Themes derived from this study were cross compared with existing literature to determine if they corroborate previously published views.

The main findings from this study were the ineffectiveness of current legislation and anti-spiking measures in protecting women and girls against spiking, prompting a need for change. The overarching finding from this study was the need for the introduction of a specific spiking law, which would benefit reporting, police data collection and spiking services. It would aid in deterring spiking perpetrators by introducing set tariff sanctions, a factor which is currently ambiguous. Currently, most spiking messaging focuses on victims' behaviours over perpetrators' actions (Home Affairs committee, 2022). But most importantly it would allow for education into the impact on women and girls and assist provision of adequate support post-offence (Home Office, 2024).

These proposals would raise the profile and understanding of spiking and provoke public disapproval for spiking. In turn, this would deter victim blaming and reduce the shame typically felt by the victims of spiking (Sheard, 2011).

Recommendations made to increase protection of women and girls include new legislation, mandatory measures and implements that should work alongside this. These include the availability of physical inhibitors to spiking at venues including cup covers and the need for increased and more thorough searches on arrival at a venue. This would restrict substances and instruments facilitating spiking entering a venue. However, in isolation these measures alone do not fix the issue of spiking.

Participants unanimously agreed on the need for better public knowledge and education on spiking. This might be delivered with educational classes, changes in government legislation and wider campaigns of awareness. Alongside a general need for more understanding of this crime, participants argued support staff, specifically door staff and medical personnel, needed better education on spiking. Participants claimed the hostility and scepticism shown towards spiking victims by those meant to help causes extreme harm, pushing the narrative spiking is not serious, and encourages victim-blaming.

Women are continuously made to feel unsafe in the night-time economy, cautious of harm to themselves, yet wary of blame if they encounter harm. Viewing spiking with a gendered lens, including male participants trivialising spiking and disregarding its impact, highlighted a need for male education. In a male populated night-time economy men must learn to support women when vulnerable and victimised.

This study supplements the limited literature available on spiking and the current challenges on protecting women and girls. This project sheds light on the various ways women are impacted by spiking, directly and indirectly, and the failure of legislation to address this currently. By addressing the gap in legislation, and complexities regarding its comprehension and clarity, society is better informed. Spiking needs to be recognised according to the severity of its impacts on victims. This research project aims to highlight a area of violence against women which has been swept under the carpet for too long.

Despite the perspective this study takes, anyone can be the victim of spiking, and everyone deserves to be protected against it. The gendered lens was taken for this project to highlight a particular sector of society and the impacts spiking has on them. This should not be regarded as a crime against women alone but a crime that disproportionately affects women.

Due to time constraints, the survey sample is small and arguably not representative of wider society. Yet from a small sample key findings have been developed, arguing a case for devoting more time and resources to a larger scale research project. For the avoidance of harm and ethical considerations this research project looks at spiking without the involvement and insight of those who have been victim to the crime. Further research should be done involving these women as they can provide in-depth experience of the victimisation of spiking. This should be done with great consideration and care.

Legislation needs to be amended, at least to better address spiking. The introduction of a spiking specific law has been proposed by the Labour government. Alongside this, the government must implement the recommendations above to allow women to feel reassured that this crime is no longer being marginalised and that these violations against women's lives are not condoned. Hopefully society will take violence against women and girls seriously as more legislation is created, and information collected and published. It is highly likely that spiking will continue to take place and cannot be entirely erased, but with harsher punishment, new legislation, mandatory regulations and public rejection, women will be safer than they have been.

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